

Effective Use of Teaching Methods in Physical Education Lessons

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Abstract: When teaching physical education to children, the teacher requires experience and pedagogical skills. The article examines the aspects of the effective use of teaching methods in physical education lessons.

Keywords: Physical education, innovation, methodology, sports, teacher, teaching methods, educational effectiveness, healthy lifestyle.

INTRODUCTION

Decrees and resolutions have been issued in our country to develop sports, which have created a great foundation for the development of physical education and sports, and at the same time, for the formation of a healthy generation. Instilling a love for physical education and sports in every person begins in the family. Most importantly, physical education and sports, as one of the foundations of a healthy lifestyle, serve to increase the potential and competence of young people, as well as their physical and spiritual development.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Continuous engagement in physical education and sports stimulates the child both physically and spiritually, and his whole body develops harmoniously. "Resolution No. 118 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2019 "On approval of the Concept of Development of Physical Education and Mass Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2023" provides for the development and introduction of innovative forms and mechanisms that ensure the broad coverage of all segments of the population, especially young people, with physical education and mass sports. organization is a priority task."

The health-improving and educational tasks of physical education are as follows:

- you will be in a good mood throughout the day;
- your work will be productive, your creative activity will be strong;
- the nervous system becomes balanced, you become calm, thoughtful;
- forms feelings of activity, initiative, difficulty, cheerfulness, friendship;
- regular physical exercise leads to the formation of hygienic skills;
- the fat in the body decreases, you become slim, agile, and agile; - your muscles tighten, your figure becomes beautiful and toned;
- blood circulation in the vessels improves, the supply of oxygen and nutrients to the body

and organs improves; - the body's defenses increase;

- you look younger, more beautiful, more active and healthier than others. Among the methods of physical fitness, morning physical education is of great importance.

The effectiveness of teaching in the lessons depends on the observance of educational principles, as well as on the correct choice of teaching methods and techniques. Method (Greek) - a way to achieve a specific goal, perform a specific task, a set of methods for practical or theoretical mastery (knowledge) of something. The pedagogical meaning of the concept of method is to arm oneself with knowledge, skills, abilities and apply them in practice. It is recommended to study teaching methods in the following types:

1. Methods related to the teacher's activity;

2. Methods related to the student's activity. An attempt to deeply study, develop and bring the above-mentioned traditional teaching methods closer to universal teaching methods will yield the following results:

1. The method of arming with ready-made knowledge: - based on textbooks and teaching aids; - based on didactic aids with demonstration.

2. Guided learning method. Stimulating student activity based on step-by-step, systematic guided (written and oral) tasks.

3. Problem-based learning method.

4. Conscious - verbal cognitive learning method. (Discovery learning method). Based on the above teaching methods, student activity can be described as follows:

1. The method of conscious observation and retention in memory.

2. The method of searching and drawing conclusions using guided tasks, the method of discussion and debate.

4. The method of discovery (text creation) through independent and creative research.

Using the above methods, students form their knowledge, skills and abilities, and engage in practical and creative application.

The method of arming with ready-made knowledge is one of the oldest and most proven methods in the education system. When working with this method, the teacher does not overload himself: he recommends completing previously prepared, understandable tasks and exercises for the student. Educational and technical means are effectively used. The teaching method, which is a structural element of the pedagogical system in physical education lessons, is important in ensuring the result of this process, that is, the goal of the lesson. The effective implementation of pedagogical technologies in the process of training leads to the independent activity of students in the educational process. In conclusion, it can be emphasized that all components of education should be organized in such a way that, along with providing students with deep and fundamental knowledge, they also teach them to think broadly. Because the need for independent learning in the student during the educational process is a requirement of the present day. The main task of pedagogical technology is to ensure the achievement of educational goals through the development of students' knowledge.

In the process of physical education, the main activity of the teacher is carried out with the word: with the help of the word, knowledge is given, understanding is activated and deepened, tasks are given, their implementation is controlled, the results are analyzed and evaluated, and the discipline of children is controlled. The word solves the necessary task in understanding, evaluating and self-managing the activities of the participants. At the same time, the word, depending on its use, consists of one or another deductive story, conversation, discussion, etc.

The effectiveness of teaching in the lessons, along with the observance of the principles of

teaching, also depends on the correct choice of teaching methods and techniques. Method (Greek) - a set of methods for achieving a specific goal, performing a specific task, practical or theoretical assimilation (knowledge) of something. The pedagogical meaning of the concept of method is to arm with knowledge, skills, competencies and apply them in practice.

It is recommended to study teaching methods by dividing them into the following types:

1. Methods related to the teacher's activity;
2. Methods related to the student's activity.

An attempt to deeply study, develop, and bring the above-mentioned traditional teaching methods closer to universal teaching methods yields the following results:

3. The method of purposeful creative activity aimed at solving a problem.
 1. The method of equipping with ready-made knowledge:
 - ✓ based on textbooks and teaching aids;
 - ✓ based on didactic aids with demonstrations.
 2. Guided learning method. Stimulating student activity based on stage-by-stage, systematic guided (written and oral) tasks.
 3. Problem-based learning method.
 4. Conscious - verbal cognitive learning method. (Discovery learning method).

Based on the above teaching methods, the student's activity can be described as follows.

1. The method of conscious observation and retention in memory.
2. The method of searching and drawing conclusions using guided tasks, the method of discussion and debate.
3. The method of purposeful creative activity aimed at solving a problem.
4. The method of discovery (text creation) through independent and creative research.

Students, using the above methods, form their knowledge, skills and abilities, and engage in practical and creative application.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be emphasized that all aspects of education should be organized in such a way that, while providing students with deep and fundamental knowledge, they also teach them to think broadly. Because the need for independent learning in the student during the educational process is a requirement of the present day. Therefore, the main task of pedagogical technology is to ensure the achievement of educational goals through the development of students' knowledge.

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